

Technology of Use of Hadith Examples in Spiritual and Moral Education of Students

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ABSTRACT: This article is mainly aimed at reinforcing education and humanity in the process of spiritual and moral development during the globalization, mainly in the course of the current scientific and technological tendencies, and their solution of the use of hadith examples in educational classes. The information included and the use of harmoniously developed generation is illuminated with examples of the current issues.

KEYWORDS: Education, Spirituality, Enlightenment, Moralism, Hadith, Sunnah, Globalization, Integration, Validity, Traditions

INTRODUCTION

The independence of our republic was the most important aspect of reforms, ensuring the needs of the state, the formation of the material base and the base of ancient traditions and educational technology marked with an action to strengthen it. The recovery of scientific, religious, educational and cultural heritage, national values and traditions, and the education of customs has risen to the level of state policy. Lots of efforts were put in this area, plans for state significance and a number of laws, decisions and decrees of our state and government were developed.

In particular, the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on May 3, 2019 "On Improving the Efficiency of Spiritual and Enlightenment and Development of the Sector Development, Decisions of the Cabinet of Measures of the Cabinet of Ministers of Uzbekistan, The ideas of professors from professors in the implementation of the tasks of November 1, 2018th, on "On measures to organize and support the school of ancestors and the use of the national scientific heritage in educating students, The main goals of them are the priority of spirituality" and others confirm the actuality of the following area.

THE MAIN FINDINGS AND RESULTS

The occurring globalization in the history of scientific and technical development requires the formation of civil society, the qualities of spirituality, mental perfection, and the world-making, to create pedagogical solutions to them to encourage social activism, ideological struggle. Therefore, young people have chosen socio-pedagogical and pedagogical urgent tasks to establish strategic and tactical goals of the development of spiritual and moral worldwide to achieve them. Studies for spiritual and moral upbringing play an important role in the structure of the world's research.

The following research leads the spiritual and moral education, nationals and cultural heritage, Islamic customs, Islamic traditions and the hadith of our faithful scholars. This, in turn, is being implemented directly to the formation of philosophical, legacy, morally, religious, artistic, religious ideas and concepts, and the implementation of socially active responses to events in society. Today, comprehensive structure in priorities such as the physical, intellectual, spiritual heritage of the younger generation and the sources of Islamic culture are being carried out in the spirit of respect for national and universal values.

"... Preservation of the historical heritage, customs and national education traditions of our people, the wide range of measures to strengthen inter-religious tutorships, interethnic harmony and mutual love atmosphere" says our President. In this regard, Muhammad ibn Ismail Al-Bukhari, imam Abu Josh al-Hakim, the younger generation in scientific works of Muhammad ibn Al-Tirmimi, a pedagogy of the younger generation in spiritual and moral education are in the main component. The moral aspects of professional qualifications, social knowledge, who serve the scientific heritage of scientists, especially the conduction and manners are of particular attention to solutions, especially the scientific heritage of scientists.

Here comes the question "What is spirituality?". The word "spirituality" is a majority of "non-material things" meaning human etiquette, ethics, inner and spiritual world, that is, the condition of a man. When it means "spirituality" man's spiritual

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world, the whole mind, worldview should be understood. As our great philosopher Alisher Navoi said, "the meaning of the word spiritual means a perfect person entering the path of truth".

An online meeting was held on January 19, 2021 by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoev in this regard. At the meeting, the President said: "If the body of society is the economy, and its soul is spirituality. It is known that today the world is rapidly struggling, and the conflict of interest is growing. The structural processes are also causing unexpected problems with the incomparable new opportunities for humanity. Threats and risks against national identity and spiritual values are increasingly growing. He noted only in a mood of people in different ways, especially in different ways in different ways to think of self-thought, leaving me".

The number of analysis of the socio-technical environment is demanding. It is also given that spirituality and enlightenment is not based on this area. Therefore, the Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment is also critical in studying the field and radically improved its activities. The President said that on the basis of the educational institution of the Center, the organization of socio-spiritual research was invited to the institution of socio-spiritual research.

Measures have been identified to raise spiritual and educational work in quality and content to a new level. The Republican Center for Spirituality and Enlightenment was established that the spiritual and educational activities of all regional councils, ministries, agencies and organizations. The material and technical support of the organizations in the center and its system has been dramatically intensified. "There is no break in the process of education", says wise people. However, the community in spiritual and educational work is not perfect yet. In this regard, the kindergarten, school, higher education, the neighborhood are working interconnected.

Therefore, it is noted that creating a single system of spiritual and educational work, in particular, the importance of raising boys and girls through childhood in moral and virtuous atmosphere, providing uninterrupted methodological assistance to all educational institutions. There are also instructions to increase the effectiveness of spiritual and educational work in schools, secondary special and higher education institutions. All university and their branches, the post of the Vice-Rector for Youth issues and spiritual and educational work within the existing state units.

Particular attention was paid to ensuring the sustainability of socio-spiritual environment in the neighborhood. The professor and famous intellectuals were flooded in each neighborhood based on the spiritual sponsor of one "mahalla". The center of the regions was instructed to build spirituality and enlightenment facilities on the basis of the standard design, and the allocation of additional States in the field is provided.

Increasing the efficiency of national idea and promotion, spiritual and educational work, in order to further develop literature and reading in the community, the fund of spiritual and creative support was established. From the 2021/2022 academic year, the inclusion of specialization in the field of spirituality and enlightenment was established, preparing mature personnel in this direction.

"The issue of spirituality acts of relevant ministries and agencies. All this is one of the most important", says the President.

As the first President Islam Karimov said, "Spirituality, people, society, the state are the power. Consequently, if spiritual cultgestivity of people, the spiritual culture of people, the more popularity of our country are higher, it is easier to solve other social problems. The concept of spirituality includes the word enlightenment. The word "Enlightenment" is also comes from the verb "Arafa" meaning "to know, learn, get acquainted". In general, its lexical meaning is knowledge. As the term, it states a diversity of a variety of sciences, the essence of nature. Spirituality is a continuous, action process. The individuals of spiritual and enlightenment introduce the country. Spirituality begins with educational education. It is clear that there is no need to be educated.

What is morality? The words morality, behavior and signs are Arabic words and are also used in Uzbek. Ethics is a social conscious uniform, which consists of principles, requirements, norms, and rules that can lead to human behavior in all areas of social life. Consisting of a "moral society, good, fair, promise, conscience, belief, love, commitment", as ensured in the understanding of human behavior, norms reflected. All of these moral concepts are of evaluated nature. The great scientist Imam Ghazali said, "Even if a person and man are in one sign of immorality, this man is considered immoral."

Not only in the formation of moral consciousness and moral feelings in the moral education of the younger generation, but the most importantly, they can involve students in different types of activities that appear their spiritual. The moral relationship is an attitude to society, work, people and everyone.

The development of society shows that in countries where the spirituality developed widespread, the construction of a fair society can be formed loving people in it. In such a society, the nation and the people will be strong, the pursuit of creativity will grow. We all know that in the teaching of Islam, the main source is "the Qur'an" and then hadiths. The words "hadith" or "Sunnah" have the same meaning and the words of our Prophet Muhammad, and exemplary words, in the hadiths representing faith, purity and moral qualities, in the hadiths related to His name is embodied.

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Hadiths on spiritual and educational and moral traditions have been used in the teaching of all Islamic and destructive states and peoples for thousands of years. Samples from hadiths regarding spiritual and educational and moral heritage: "He cannot leave his child otherwise to mankind." That is, a parent said that the good legacy that leaves into society itself is not the possessor, state, wealth, but a manifestation.

"There is no salvation other than science and will be". From any ignorance, knowledge saves enlightenment. The unemployed person does not recognize God or the defects and riots in the world come from ignorance and upgrading. "Science is better than prayer and piety" put knowledge in the same extent, "he preferred to prayer even though he prayed. Because the prayer is given to personal work and interest, knowledge is expected to benefit society and all mankind. Therefore, the objection to the knowledge is preferred to prayer.

"All living things ask forgiveness, and even the sea fish." Because knowledge is even in favor of creatures are also interested in the education. Incipient demand is an obligation for every Muslim and a man. That is, it is impossible to imagine the society and the bright future without knowledge of knowledge to knowledge".

It is said to the escalation of knowledge and ignorance of ignorance leads to a spiritual moral crisis of society. Therefore, "Be scientific and obedient knowledge, do not be the leader of it. The disaster of the science is to be free of charge. It is emphasized that knowledge is emphasized only on people who are eager to repeat knowledge".

The main directions of the hadiths depict by spiritual and moral education is shown in the following table:

Table 1. The main directions of hadiths reflecting spiritual and moral education.

"Be a scholar to become learner, or learn knowledge, or be a listener, or be love for knowledge and heritage. Do not be the fifth, to perish" says hadith. In this, the interests of knowledge were raised so high that four ways will be interested in science. Because not everyone can be a scientist but can listen to science, love for knowledge to the people of science and serve the scientist also is also interested.

The hadiths of spiritual and moral education are condemned if moral qualities such as goodness, chastity, thanks, and greed, and the succession of moral emotions, sarcastic emotions, intelligence. Hadiths contain instructions that will be theoretical and practical basis for spiritual and moral education of young people. Of these, the rational use of the spiritual and moral education of the students will serve to form a comprehensive, moral, spiritual, physical, full-fled, patriot, hardworking, patriot, mature developed generation.

CONCLUSION

The opening of the essence of spiritual and moral education in the hadiths is refused to imitate our ancestors, which inherited blind-religious attacks, and our young people in contradicting to national and religious values. Probably kindness is in peace and faithfulness. Based on the above considerations, the student's introduction of "Continuous spirituality" in all areas of higher education institutions is the spiritual examination of students, especially from the hadith examples of spiritual and moral rhetorics. These all can claim the use of modernity is one of the most pressing issues today.

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